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Comparative Analysis of Psychometric Properties of Multiple-Choice Test Items Question in Economics Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations, Kwara State

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Abstract

This study examined the comparative analysis of psychometric properties of multiple-choice test items in Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations in Economics, Kwara State. Reliability coefficient, difficulty levels, discriminating power and effectiveness of distracter of West African Examinations Council (WAEC), National Examinations Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) Senior School Certificate Examinations SSCE in Economics multiple choice items were examined and compared. The study employed descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study, which was carried out in 20 randomly selected public senior secondary schools in Kwara State. Three hundred and seventy-six (Male 180 and Female 180) senior secondary school class three (SSIII) Economics students during the 2022/2023 academic session were sampled using multi-stage sampling techniques. 2022 Multiple-choice Economics items were administered to students in their classes to collect data. Item analysis was done using Excel and SPSS software packages while the results were analysed using frequency count, mean rating and analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 alpha level of significance. Among the findings, NECO items were found to be more reliable than those of WAEC and NABTEB, while WAEC items exhibited higher discrimination levels. NABTEB items were noted to be more difficult. It is concluded that all three examination bodies are equally valid and reliable, urging stakeholders to view them as partners in the nation's educational development rather than as superior or inferior entities. Recommendations include promoting collaboration among the examination bodies to enhance the overall quality of assessments.

Keyword: Analysis, Comparative, Co-efficient, Discriminating power & Reliability

Introduction

In Nigeria, educational assessment is being conducted at schools and at national level and it is based on prescribed curriculum of the school system. At the school level, the teacher gets information on pupils' performance and such information is being interpreted and used for improving both teaching and learning activities (Haruna, 2019). Educational assessments at the national level are tested for selection and certification in Nigeria. At this national level, educational assessment is in the form of public examination such as West African Examinations Council (WAEC), National Examinations Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). Thus, the qualification for admission into any higher educational institution is the school certificate issued by the West African School Certificate Examinations Council (WAEC), the National Examinations Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). West African Examinations Council (WAEC), National Examinations Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) are the three examining bodies charged with the responsibilities of conducting final examination and evaluating final year students in Senior Secondary Schools and Technical Colleges in Nigeria respectively.

In the light of the above, Evaluation agencies are examining bodies which are tasked with maintaining a common standard in the development and administration of public examinations. A study by Nworgu (2006), reported that evaluation agencies were set up to promote education, co-ordinate educational programmes, and to control and monitor the quality of education in the institutions of learning, with the essence of organizing public examinations in order to provide uniform standards to all examinees, irrespective of the type or method of instruction they have received. The main examination bodies in Nigeria include the West African Examinations Council (WAEC), the National Examination Council (NECO) and the National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). A critical observation of the operations of these boards

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reveals that they perform similar functions. For instance, all conduct secondary school graduate certification, although in the case of NABTEB, the examination is reserved for final year students of Nigerian Technical and Vocational Colleges.

Therefore, the assemblage of subject examinations conducted by these examining bodies is known as the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) and serves as an end-of-course evaluation for all secondary school graduates. The purpose of this examination is to ascertain to what extent students have achieved educational objectives in a particular course (Offor, 2001). In view of the economic and social importance attached to senior secondary school certificates and the opportunities to proceed to higher institutions for those who possess such certificates, the awarding of this certificate is one of the most important events in the Nigerian academic calendar. It thus goes without saying that much is expected from the certificate examining and awarding bodies, in ensuring that the spirit and focus of the examinations are not misplaced.

West African Examinations Council (WAEC), National Examinations Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) conduct standardized tests and standardized tests are known to possess psychometric properties before it could be judged worthwhile. These tests could be in essay or objective form. Essay tests are test items where the testees candidates are allowed to answer the questions with sentences composed and organized by them (Nkwocha, 2004). On the other hand, objective tests are tests in which every question is set in such a way as to have only one correct answer. The opinion of the examiner is not required to judge the correctness of the answer. One example of an objective test is multiple-choice tests which contain items that are usually with four to five plausible answer options from which testees candidates are expected to recognize the correct answer.

Nevertheless, multiple choice testing is one of the most commonly used assessment formats particularly in public examinations; it consists of a stem and a set of plausible options. The stem presents the item as a problem to be solved, a question or an incomplete statement to be completed and the options are the possible answers that the examinee can choose from, with only one correct answer called the key and the incorrect answers called the distracters (Morrison & Free, 2001). Therefore, in order to be sure of the true performance of the testees candidates in any examination, there is a need to ascertain the quality of the examination (test) which indicates the psychometric properties of the test items. Psychometric properties of the test items cannot be over-emphasis because the considerations of validity and reliability typically are viewed as essential elements for determining the quality of any test. However, professional and practitioner associations frequently have placed these concerns within broader contexts when developing standards and making overall judgments about the quality of any test as a whole within a given context.

The field of psychometrics is primarily concerned with the construction and validation of measurement instruments such as test, questionnaires and personality inventories. Also, one of the theoretical approaches in psychometrics is Classical test theory, which involves the validity and reliability of an item. In classical test theory, the psychometric properties of objective items are determined through item analysis and test analysis, Item analysis is a general term used to describe a set of statistical techniques employed to evaluate test items (Cohen, Swerdlik & Sturman, 2013). According to Anastasi and Urbina (2014); Anikweze (2012) and Denga (2003) items could be analysed qualitatively, in terms of their content and form, and quantitatively, in terms of their statistical properties. Thus, psychometric properties are those aspects of a test that explain how good a test is, they deal with things like the reliability and validity of a test.

The psychometric properties that every measuring instrument such as a test should possess are validity and reliability. Robson (2011) defined validity as a measure of the extent to which the test (or an instrument) measures what it intends to measure. Enyi (2002) further observed that if a test possesses other qualities but lacks validity, the test will be considered as not being useful. Validity is the watchword or foundational stone over which the entire superstructure of testing is based (Sidhu, 2005). Onah (2014) therefore, stated that tests are required to be valid if results based on them are going to be utilized for value judgment. If an item is valid, such an item is said to be reliable to a greater extent. On the other hand, reliability of a test refers to the degree to which a test measures accurately and consistently yielding comparable results when administered a number of times (Akuezuilo & Agu, 2003) cited in Juliet (2018). A test validity and reliability can be ascertained through item analysis among others.

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In view of this, Nwaobia (1990) cited in Bandele and Adewale (2013) stated that item analysis is concerned with ascertaining the worth of test items. Item analysis involves quantitative computation used to verify how each test item measures effectively the construct it is designed to measure. Item analysis helps to improve a test by revising or discarding ineffective items, provide diagnostic information on what examinees know and what they do not know. Item analysis usually calls for the computation of some indices such as difficulty index, discrimination index, and distracter effectiveness (Okoye, 1996) cited in (Ugama, 2017).

These indices of item analysis will now be explained one after the other. Therefore, the difficulty of a test item is normally determined from the proportion of the total group selecting the correct answer to that item (Hotiu, 2006). Item difficulty is the percentage of students that correctly answered the item, also referred to as the P-value. The range is from 0% to 100%, the higher the value, the easier the item. P-values above 0.90 are very easy items and might be a concept not worth testing. P-values below 0.20 indicate difficult items and should be reviewed for possible confusing language or the contents needs re-instruction. Optimum difficulty level is 0.50 for maximum discrimination between high and low achievers. For example an item answered correctly by 70% examinees has a difficulty index of 0.70. If 90% of a standard group pass an item, it is easy; if only 10% pass, the item is hard or too difficult. Generally, items of moderate difficulty are to be preferred to those which are much easier or much harder.

Secondly, Item discrimination is a measure of how well the item discriminates between examinees who are well knowledgeable in the content area and those who are not (Professional Testing, 2010). The extent to which a test item discriminates between those in the upper third and the lower third, respectively is its discrimination power (Ede, 2019). It also refers to the ability of an item to differentiate among students on the basis of how well they know the material being tested. This value ranges between 0.0 and 1.00, also referred to as the D-value. Higher the value, more discrimination of the item is. A highly discriminating item indicates that the students who had high tests scores got the item correct whereas students who had low test scores got the item incorrect. Lastly, Distracters are classified as the incorrect answer in a multiple-choice question. According to Instructional Assessment Resources (IAR, 2011), student performance in an exam item are very much influence by the quality of the given distracters. Analysis of distracters can function as a valuable indicator of item difficulty, a good quality distractor should be selected by those who perform poorly and should be ignored by those who perform well. If a distractor is chosen more often than the correct answer, this may indicate poor instructions or a misleading question.

Non- function distractors are those options that are selected by less than 5% of the examinees. These non-function distractors may have no connection or having some clues, which are not directly related to the correct answer. Distractors that are not chosen or are consistently chosen by only less than 5% of the examinee are obviously ineffective and should be omitted or replaced (Hamza etal, 2014). Hence, it is necessary to determine the effectiveness of each item provided distractor as an addition to the item difficulty analysis.

Items considered suitable and acceptable are stored in the database ready for use in any examination. Extraction of the items to be used can be done easily and can be passed on for typesetting in readiness for printing. Collation of items by many people as the case with manual method is eliminated. Incidence of paper leakage is reduced or eliminated at this stage. Test items for selection are evaluated. They are either considered as worthy or unworthy of inclusion in the item bank. The items considered worthy are either accepted for direct use without any revision or for further post editing before being put into use. Item can be considered as unworthy and discarded. Unworthy items are those that do not focus on the central concept or requiring too much revision and considered rejected. The items for further post editing may require minor, fair or major revision. The revision is minor if action needed is insertion of articles, correction of spellings and punctuation. It is fair if it requires re-ordering, removal of words and replacement of one distractor at most. The revision is a major one if it involves more substantial grammatical revision and replacement of two or more of the distracters (Borkinni, 2009).

However, the position of Economics as a subject in secondary school curriculum has been strengthened because it has been accepted that it has some civil values based on some topics such as "the element and determinants of national income, the structure and activities of labour unions, the working and influence of financial institution". These prepared one adequately for life in modern society (Obemeata1991) cited in (Idika, 2020). According to Adu (2002), the study of economics serves a useful

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purpose in modern life. It gives us facts and shows us what may be expected to be the outcome of certain lines of conduct; it helps us to decide which of several alternatives to choose. It charged its recipient to make wise choice that will satisfy their needs in the presence of unlimited wants and resources. Despite the relevance of Economics to everyday life in the area of commerce and industry, Adu and Ayeni (2004) demonstrated that achievement of candidates in Economics is not only poor generally but continues to fall over the years in a study on an “Appraisal of Trends in Achievement of Students in Economics at the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination in Oyo State.”

However, despite the fact that the certificate being awarded by these three examining bodies are said to be equivalent, yet, stakeholders in the education sector doubts the equivalence. The criticisms against these examining bodies gave the researcher a lot of concern. Based on these, the researcher therefore, examine and compare psychometric properties of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB economics achievement examinations so as to know whether there exist any relationship between their difficulty levels, discrimination power, distracter index, and reliability coefficient and finally to find out whether their economics multiple choice items are equivalent test items.

Statement of the Research Problem

This research addresses the issue of standard comparability across different tests used by various Nigerian examination bodies, focusing on the quality of multiple choice questions. It advocates for the comparative analysis of these items based on psychometric properties such as reliability, item difficulty, item discrimination, and item distracters (Bandeale & Adewale, 2013).

Previous studies have analyzed the psychometric properties of senior school certificate multiple choice test items, yet gaps remain. Bandeale and Adewale's (2013) research compared WAEC, NECO, and NABTEB's mathematics exams, but did not consider item analysis or Economics Achievement Examinations. Similarly, Mahmud-Jamiu's (2012) analysis of the psychometric characteristics of Economics Objective Test Items did not involve a comparative analysis of WAEC, NECO, and NABTEB. Olatunji's (2009) investigation on the effect of option number on psychometric properties also left out NABTEB when comparing Economics multiple choice papers.

These previous works, while representing significant contributions to the field, did not conduct a comparative analysis of the psychometric properties of the three major Nigerian examining bodies for Secondary Schools in Economics. Moreover, none of these studies investigated all four measures of item analysis. This research work aims to fill these gaps, providing a comprehensive and comparative analysis of the psychometric properties of multiple choice questions across these examination bodies.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study were to juxtapose:

1. The reliability levels of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items.
2. The item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items.
3. The item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Achievement Examinations.
4. The item functionality level of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What are the reliability levels of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items in terms of equivalence among secondary school students in kwara state?
- ii. What are the differences in the difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state?
- iii. What are the differences in the discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state?

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- iv. Do distracters of each item in WAEC, NECO and NABTEB function equally among secondary school students in kwara state?

Research Hypotheses

The study was anchored on the following hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference in the item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state.
2. There is no significant difference in the item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state.

Research Methodology

The descriptive research design was adopted for this study. The population for this study consists all public senior secondary school students in Kwara State. There are 347 public Senior Secondary Schools and 5 Technical School in Kwara State which make the total number to be 352 public schools. However, the target population for this study consists all the 2014/2015 final year students in Public Senior Secondary Schools and Technical College in Kwara State. This target population consists all the 16,996 final year students. The proposed sample for this study made up of 376 students which were selected using multi-stage sampling technique (www.raosoft.com/samplecalculator). Multi-stage sampling technique was used for this study as follows:

At the first stage, stratified random sampling technique was adopted to stratify the four (4) local government areas with eighty-eight (88) public secondary schools within the Kwara Central Senatorial Districts in Kwara State as stated below;

- 1) Asa Local Government Area with fifteen (15) public senior secondary schools
- 2) Ilorin East Local Government Area with twenty-seven (27) public secondary schools
- 3) Ilorin South Local Government with twenty-one (22) public senior secondary schools
- 4) Ilorin West Local Government Area with twenty-four (24) public senior secondary schools

The researcher selects five (5) public senior secondary schools from each stratum. Thus, a total of twenty (20) public senior secondary schools in Kwara Central Senatorial District were randomly selected. At the second stage, purposive sampling technique was used as the researcher purposively selects SS3 class from the chosen schools. This class was selected because the students are expected to have covered a major part of the school certificate Economics syllabus. They are in the best position to respond to the tests prepared for this research work because they are preparing for their WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics examinations.

At the third stage, simple random technique was used to select nineteen (19) students who offer Economics from the three (3) arms (Art, Commercial and Science class) in each school. The instruments that were used for data collection in this study are WAEC, NECO and NABTEB multiple Economics papers. These three Economics Multiple Choice Question paper were adopted in their original form, with NECO Question paper having 60 items and both the WAEC and NABTEB Question paper having 50 items each respectively. The instruments are standardized test which are presumed to be content valid. In computing the reliability of these research instruments, split-half method was employed to test internal consistency of the instruments. In administering the instrument, the researcher collected an introductory letter from the head of department of Social Sciences Education which was presented to the principal of each of the selected schools to seek permission of the school authorities. Date and time slated for the administration of the test was fixed, and duration for the test administration was last for 1 hour in their various classes with the help of research assistant and Economics teachers in the school. The data collected were scored in dichotomous and polytomous form which were used to carry out item analysis (reliability coefficient, difficulty levels, discriminating power and effectiveness of distracter) using Excel and SPSS software packages. The results obtained from the item analysis were used to provide answers to the research questions using Descriptive statistics (frequency counts and mean rating) and inferential statistics (ANOVA) was used to test the hypotheses postulated at 0.05 level of significant while split-half method was used to determine the reliability co-efficient.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What are the reliability levels of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items in terms of equivalence among secondary school students in kwara state?

Table 1: Reliability Levels of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items

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Examination	NO	Reliability
WAEC	50	0.76
NECO	60	0.78
NABTEB	50	0.75

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 1 show the comparison of the reliability of 2022 WAEC, NECO AND NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. From the Table 1, it can be observed that WAEC SSCE Economics items had reliability of 0.76; NECO SSCE Economics items had reliability of 0.78 while NABTEB SSCE Economics items had reliability of 0.75. The results show that these three (3) examinations are reliable, but there is difference in their reliability with NECO Economics Multiple Choice Test Items having more reliable test items than WAEC and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items with a reliability value of 0.78.

Research Question 2: What are the differences in the difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state?

Table 2: Results of Item Difficulty of 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items

Ranges of Difficulty	WAEC Frequency	%	NECO Frequency	%	NABTEB Frequency	%	Description
0-14%	0	0	0	0	1	2	V. Difficult
15%-29%	16	32	31	52	12	24	Difficult
30%-69%	34	68	27	45	34	68	Moderately Difficult
70%-84%	0	0	0	0	1	2	Easy
85%-100%	0	0	2	3	2	4	V. Easy
Total	50	100	60	100	50	100	

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 2 show the item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. Results revealed that for WAEC; no item 0 (0%) was very difficult, 16 (32%) of the items were difficult, 34 (68%) of the items were moderately difficult, no item 0 (0%) was easy and no item 0 (0%) was very easy. For NECO; no item 0 (0%) was very difficult, 31 (52%) of the items were difficult, 27 (45%) of the items were moderately difficult, no item 0 (0%) was easy and 2 (3%) of the items were very easy. On the other hand, for NABTEB 1 (2%) of the items was very difficult, 12 (24%) of the items were difficult, 34 (68%) of the items were moderately difficult, 1 (2%) of the items was easy and 2 (4%) of the items were very easy. However, results in Table 3 below compare the mean (x) of **item difficulty indices** of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items.

Table 3: Results of Mean Difficulty Indices of 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items

Examination	No of Item	Mean Difficulty
WAEC	50	0.34
NECO	60	0.32
NABTEB	50	0.40

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 3 show the comparison of item difficulty in 2022 WAEC, NECO AND NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. From the Table 3, it can be observed that WAEC SSCE Economics items had mean difficulty of 0.34; NECO SSCE Economics items had mean difficulty of 0.32 while NABTEB SSCE Economics items had mean difficulty of 0.40. This means that there is difference in their difficulty indices with NABTEB SSCE Economics items had the highest mean difficulty of 0.40 and the results also imply that NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice items have more difficulty items than WAEC and NECO Economics Multiple choice Test Items.

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Research Question 3: What are the differences in the discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state?

Table 4: Results of Discrimination Power of 2014 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items.

Ranges of Discrimination Index	WAEC Frequency	%	NECO Frequency	%	NABTEB Frequency	%	Description
-0.00-0.18	15	30	18	30	24	48	Poor
0.19-0.29	9	18	18	30	17	34	Moderate
0.30-0.39	10	20	14	23	5	10	Good
0.40-1.00	16	32	10	17	4	8	V. good
Total	50	100	60	100	50	100	

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 4 show the discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. Results revealed that for WAEC; 15 (30%) of the items were poor, 9 (18%) of the items were moderate, 10 (20%) of the items were good and 16 (32%) of the items were very good. For NECO; 18 (30%) of the items were poor, 18 (30%) of the items were moderate, 14 (23%) of the items were good and 10 (17%) of the items were very good. Also, for NABTEB, 24 (48%) of the items were poor, 17 (34%) of the items were moderate, 5 (10%) of the items were good and 4 (8%) of the items were very good. However, results in Table 5 below compare the mean (x) of item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items.

Table 5: Results of Mean Discrimination Power of 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items.

Examination	NO	Mean Discrimination
WAEC	50	0.30
NECO	60	0.27
NABTEB	50	0.21

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 5 show the comparison of item discrimination power of the 2022 WAEC, NECO AND NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. From the table, it can be observed that WAEC SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.30; NECO SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.27 while NABTEB SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.21. This means that there is difference in their discrimination power with WAEC SSCE Economics items had the highest mean discriminating value of 0.30 and the results also imply that WAEC SSCE Economics Multiple Choice items have more discrimination power than NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple choice Test Items.

Research Question 4: Do distracters of each item in WAEC, NECO and NABTEB function equally among secondary school students in kwara state?

Table 6: Results of Functional and Non-functional Options of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items

Variable	WAEC Frequency	Percentage %	NECO Frequency	Percentage %	NABTEB Frequency	Percentage %
Functional Options	148	98.7	231	96	140	93
Non-functional Options	2	1.3	9	4	10	7
Total	150	100	240	100	150	100

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

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Results in Table 6 show the item functionality level of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. Results revealed that there were 148 (98.7%) functional options and 2 (1.3%) non-functional options in 2014 WAEC SSCE Economics items, also there were 231 (96%) functional options and 9 (4%) non-functional options in 2014 NECO SSCE Economics items while there were 141 (93%) functional options and 10 (7%) non-functional options in 2014 NABTEB SSCE Economics items. The researcher compares functionality of options in WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items by using 5% of the students that selected distractors as shown in Table 7 below. However, results in Table 7 below compare the mean (\bar{x}) of results of the 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items according to number of functioning options.

Table 7: Comparison of Results of the 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items According to Number of Functioning Options

Variable	No of functional options	Percentage %
WAEC	148	98.7
NECO	231	96
NABTEB	141	94

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 7 show the comparative analysis of 2022 WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items according to number of functioning options. The result shows that WAEC had 148 (98.7%) functional options; NECO had 231 (96%) functional options while NABTEB had 141 (94%) functional options. This means that distractors of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items do not function equally and the results also imply that WAEC SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items had more functional options than NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items because its options are all functional.

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state.

Table 8: Results of ANOVA Showing Item Difficulty Indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	Sig.	Decision
Among Groups	.160	2	.080	4.403	.014	Rejected
Within Groups	2.856	157	.018			
Total	3.016	159				

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 8 show that F-value yielded 4.403 which is significant at 0.05 alpha level ($P < 0.05$). Since the calculated level of significant (0.014) is less than the critical level of significant (0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, this implies that there is a significant difference among item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Items. In order to determine the direction of this significant difference, Duncan's Post Hoc (DPH) was employed.

Table 9: Results Showing Duncan's Post Hoc (DPH) on Item Difficulty Indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items

Variable	No of Items	Post Hoc Mean Score
WAEC	50	34.24
NECO	60	32.22
NABTEB	50	39.72

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Duncan's Post Hoc (DPH) analysis revealed that the mean score for NABTEB SSCE Economics items is 39.72, significantly higher than the mean scores of WAEC and NECO SSCE Economics items, which are 34.24 and 32.22, respectively. This ranking indicates that NABTEB SSCE Economics items had the highest mean score, followed by WAEC SSCE Economics items with a mean score of 34.24, and NECO SSCE Economics items with a mean score of 32.22.

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Consequently, the hypothesis was rejected due to the significant difference observed among the item difficulty indices of WAEC, NECO, and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items.

Research Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics multiple choice test items among secondary school students in kwara state.

Table 10: Results of ANOVA Showing Item Discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	Sig.	Decision
Among Groups	.230	2	.115	6.497	.002	Rejected
Within Groups	2.776	157	.018			
Total	3.006	159				

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Results in Table 8 show that F-value yielded 6.497 which is significant at 0.05 alpha level ($P < 0.05$). Since the calculated level of significant (0.002) is less than the critical level of significant (0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, this suggests a significant difference across the item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO, and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Items. In order to determine the direction of this significant difference, Post Hoc Test (Duncan Test) was employed.

Table 9: Results Showing Duncan's Post Hoc (DPH) on Item Discrimination power of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items

Variable	No of Items	Post Hoc Mean Score
WAEC	50	30.06
NECO	60	26.80
NABTEB	50	20.64

Duncan's Post Hoc (DPH) analysis reveals that the mean score for WAEC SSCE Economics items is 30.06, significantly higher than the mean scores of NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics items, which are 26.80 and 20.64, respectively. This ranking indicates that WAEC SSCE Economics items had the highest mean score, followed by NECO SSCE Economics items with a mean score of 26.80, and NABTEB SSCE Economics items with a mean score of 20.64. Consequently, the hypothesis was rejected due to the significant difference observed among the item discrimination power of WAEC, NECO, and NABTEB SSCE Multiple Choice Economics Items.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of the study revealed that NECO Economics Multiple Choice Test Items has the highest reliability coefficient of 0.78 compared with WAEC and NABTEB reliability coefficient of 0.76 and 0.75 respectively. It might be that the much criticism by stakeholders against the three examining bodies have geared the officials toward improving the standard of these examination bodies particularly NECO. This finding is supported by Bandele and Adewale (2013) who reported that WAEC, NECO and NABTEB mathematics achievement tests were highly reliable. It also showed that the examination bodies are comparable and equivalent. This clearly contradicted the finding of Adeniran (2000) that showed that NECO is inferior to WAEC in all standards. Of recent, NECO has been criticized of poor performance such that the national assembly had to intervene on the crisis between stakeholders and officials of NECO.

Most interesting of the findings in this study is that NABTEB SSCE Economics items have more difficulty items than WAEC and NECO SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Objective test. NABTEB has of recent been rejected by some National Universities for admission purpose. It is quite often the case that criticism against examination bodies in Nigeria is centered on emotion and people that have no knowledge of the psychometric properties of examination are the loudest in the criticism. It is revealed that NABTEB outperformed WAEC and NECO in terms of difficulty of items.

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On the basis of this finding, it is quite advisable that criticism against examination bodies would be based on knowledge of facts rather than perceptions. Examinations especially Multiple Choice tests have their procedure, processes and functions. Therefore, anybody criticizing the examination must have adequate knowledge of the psychometric properties of test. Even though, the findings contradicted the work of Aborisade and Fajobi (2020) who found that no significant difference between the difficulty index of the examination items constructed by WAEC and NECO. This finding is also similar with the work of Moyinoluwa (2015) which revealed same average difficulty on four Mathematics examinations administered to SSS by NABTEB, NECO, JAMB and WAEC.

The findings of this study have further revealed that WAEC SSCE Economics items had more discriminating items than NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics items. WAEC SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.30; NECO SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.27 while NABTEB SSCE Economics items had mean discrimination power of 0.21. This finding should not be surprising because WAEC has a long history of existence; WAEC has wide area of operation and possibly more technical know-how and qualified personnel that are learned in examination psychometric properties. This finding is in line with the result of Olatunji (2009) that 4 option formats of WAEC SSCE Economics Multiple Choice tests have better discriminating indices than NECO SSCE Economics Multiple Choice tests. The result corroborate with the findings of Ogunbamowo, Adediwura and Diyan (2019) who showed that the discrimination indices of NECO and WAEC Economics test items were different from one another significantly.

It was further discovered that WAEC SSCE Economics items have more functional options than NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics items. The result showed that WAEC had 148 (98.7%) functional options; NECO had 231 (96%) functional options while NABTEB had 141 (94%) functional options. This reinforces the claim that WAEC has better facilities, personnel and excellent past records than NECO and NABTEB. This finding concurs with that of Olatunji (2009) and Abiri (2006) which revealed that 4 alternatives has the best functional options in WAEC than NECO multiple choice test item in Economics.

Similarly, findings of this study showed that there is significant difference among the difficulty and discrimination indices of WAEC; NECO and NABTEB multiple choice economics test items. This implies that the difficulty and discrimination levels of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics items are not the same. However, the Duncan post-hoc analysis shows that the significant difference noted above was accounted for by NABTEB and WAEC with higher mean difficulty and discrimination indices respectively. Finally, the findings support the claim that the three examining bodies have credibility that could be adjudged as functional and worthy of their establishment. Therefore, we should not be tied down to narrow minded critics who have no adequate knowledge of standardized examination or psychometric properties of examination.

Conclusion

It can also be concluded that there is a significant difference among difficulty and discrimination indices of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice items with NABTEB and WAEC having the highest mean difficulty and discrimination indices respectively. The findings of this study also revealed that WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Economics Multiple Choice Test Items do not function equally, with WAEC SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items having better plausible options than NECO and NABTEB SSCE Economics Multiple Choice Test Items. Finally, it could be concluded here that furthermore, multiple choice test items of the three Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations in Economics do not have the same psychometric properties in terms of reliability, item difficulty, item discrimination and effectiveness of distracters.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Examinations are highly valid and reliable and none of these examination bodies should be seen by stakeholders as being inferior or superior to the others in terms of reliability or standard, rather they should be seen as partners in progress of the nation's educational development whereas the examining bodies should improve more on the item analysis of their test items.

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2. Moderately difficult items should be given to the students so as to boost the performance of the students in various examinations and as much as possible all forms of ambiguity and bias should be avoided in the development of items.
3. Test development procedure should be strictly followed by examining body so as to arrive at item that will function effectively in differentiating between brilliant and not brilliant students. The discrimination power of the item should be ascertain to avoid redundant item.
4. The examining bodies should continue to engage the services of experts and professional in cross checking the plausibility or functionality options in a test. The key and distracters should be written in such a way that they will be equally attractive and appealing to the examinees.
5. Examination bodies should ensure that reliability level, difficulty index and discrimination power of items as well as functionality of options fall within the acceptable limits for certification at the school certification level.

References

- Abiri, J. O. O. (2007). *Elements of Evaluation Measurement and Statistical Techniques in Education*. Ilorin: University of Ilorin, Library and Publications Committee.
- Adeniran, .T. (2000): *NECO certificate valid for varsity admission*. An Article Published in the Punch Newspaper of Tuesday, 29th February, 2000. Pg 29.
- Adu, E. O. (2002). *Two problem-based learning strategies, quantitative ability and gender as determinants of students academic achievement in economics*. (Ph. D. Thesis University of Ibadan; Ibadan).
- Adu, E.O. (2004). *An Introduction to Economics Education*; A Basic Text for Tertiary Institutions Students, Ibadan: ERSO.
- Akuezuilo, E. O. &Agu, N. (2003). *Research and Statistics in Education and Social Sciences, Methods and Applications*. Awka: Nuelcenti Publishers & Academic Press Ltd.
- Anastasi, A., & Urbina, S. (2014). *Psychological Testing 7th Ed*. New Jersey; Upper Saddle River.
- Anikweze, C. M. (2012). *Measurement and Evaluation for Teacher Education, 2nd Edition*. Enugu: SNAAP Press (Nig.) Ltd.
- Bandeke, S. O., &Adewale, A. E. (2013). Comparative analysis of the item difficulty levels of WAEC, NECO and NABTEB Mathematics Achievement Examinations. *Mediterranean Journal of Social sciences*, 4(2), 761-765.
- Borokinni, O.J. (2009). Creating a database for Test Items in National Examinations. *An International Multi-Disciplinary Journal*, 3(1): 162-178.
- Burns. N. & Grove S. (2003) *Understanding Nursing Research* 3rd edition. WB Saunders Company, Philadelphia.
- Cohen, J. R., Swerdlik, M., & Sturman, E. D. (2013). *Psychological Testing and Assessment: An Introduction to Tests and Measurement*, 8th Ed. U.S.A; McGraw–Hill Companies, Inc
- Denga, D.I. (2003). *Educational Measurement, Continuous Assessment and Psychological*
- Ede, M. O. (2019). Assessment of psychometric properties of WASSCE Economics Graph related multiple-choice questions. *International Journal of Economics Education Research*, 2(1), 104-115.
- Enyi, G. S. (2002). *Introduction to Measurement and Evaluation for Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges of Education: A Professional Approach*. Enugu: Hamson Pal.
- Fan, X. (1998). Item Response Theory and Classical Test Theory: An Empirical Comparison of Their Item/Person Statistics. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 58 (3), 357-374.
- Hamza, M. A., Farah, A., Gominda, G. P., Mahummoud, S.K., &Abdulmajeed, A. (2014). The Relationship between Non-Functioning Distractors and Item Difficulty of Multiple Choice Questions: *A descriptive Analysis*. 2(4), 148-151
- Haruna, A.S. (2019). Preference for Teacher's Gender among undergraduate students of Science Education in Federal College of Education, Kano. *Kano Journal of Educational Psychology* 1 (1), 102 – 111
- Hotiu, A. (2006). *The Relationship between Item Difficulty and Discrimination Indices in Multiple-Choice Tests in a Physical Science Course*. A Thesis Submitted to the Faculty of Charles Schmidt College of Science. Florida Atlantic University, Boca Raton, Florida.
- Idika, E. O. (2020). Students' and Teachers' Factors Hindering Effective Teaching and Learning of Economics in Secondary Schools in the Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State. <https://doi.org/10.46303/jeve.2020.4>.
- Instructional Assessment Resources (2011). *Item Analysis*. Retrieved November 9, 2013 from University of Texas at Austin, Instructional Assessment Resources, IAR Web site: <http://www.utexas.edu/academic/ctl/assessment/iar/students/report/itemanalysis.pp>

Comparative Analysis of... (Ahmed, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401330>

- Juliet, O. O. (2018). Psychometric properties analysis of basic certification examination for French multiple choice test items of 2013, 2014 and 2015 in Anambra state. *Journal of Languages, Linguistics and Literary Studies (JOLLS)*, 6, 152-160.
- Morrison, S. & Free, K. (2001). Writing Multiple-Choice Test Items That Promote and Measure Critical Thinking. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 40, 17-24.
- National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) (2014). Retrieved July 13, 2014, from <http://www.nabtebnigeria.com/home.htm>
- National Examination Council (NECO) (2014). Retrieved July 13, 2014, from <http://www.neconigeria.com/history.htm>
- Nkwocha, P.C. (2004). *Measurement and Evaluation in the Field of Education*. Owerri: Versatile Publishers.
- Nwaobia, E. M. (1990). *Monograph on Introduction to Advanced Measurement and Evaluation*. University of Nigeria Nsukka.
- Nworgu, B. G. (1992) *Educational Measurement and Evaluation: Theory and Practice*. Nsukka. Hallman Publishers.
- Obemeata, J. O. [1991]. Effective Teaching of Economic in Senior Secondary School. *West African Journal of Education*. 1[1].9-13
- Offor, E. I. (2001) *Content Validity of Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) Chemistry*. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis, Faculty of Education, Imo State University, Owerri
- Ogunbamowo, A. O., Adediwura, A. A. & Diyan, R. O. (2019). Psychometric properties of 2017 West African Examination Council and National Examinations Council's Economic senior school certificate examination items. *Journal of Advances in Education and Philosophy*, 3(1), 9-18.
- Okoye, R. O. (1996). *Educational and Psychological Measurement and Evaluation*. Ikeja: ED-Solid Foundation Publishers.
- Olatunji, D. S. (2009). Effects of Number of Options on Psychometric Properties of Multiple Choice Tests in Economics. (*Med. Thesis. University of Ilorin*).
- Oluwatayo, J. A. (2004). *Mode of Entry and Performance of University Undergraduates in Science Courses*. An unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, University of Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.
- Onah, F. E. (2014). *Content Validity of Teacher Made Agricultural Science Tests Used in Secondary Schools in Enugu State*. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis. University of Nigeria Nsukka.
- Professional Testing (2010), *Building High Quality Examination Programmes*. www.proftesting.com/test_topics/steps_9.php
- Robson, C. (2011). *Real World Research: A Resource for Users of Social Research Methods in Applied Settings*, (2nd Ed.). Sussex, A. John Wiley and Sons Ltd.
- Sidhu, S. K. (2005). *New Approach to Measurement and Evaluation*. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers Ltd.
- Testing*. Calabar: Rapid Educational Publisher Ltd.
- Ugama, J. O. (2017). Investigation into the Impact of Questioning Skills in Teaching Secondary School Mathematics. *Idosr Journal of Applied Sciences* 2(3) 90-98.
- Wuddah, A. A (1994). *Difficulty and Reliability of Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) Question Papers as Functions of the Number of Option in their Multiple Choice Test*; WAEC RPAI/95. GhanaBasic.com